

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727482 (DiverIMPACTS)

DiverIMPACTS - Deliverable 1.2

**DiverIMPACTS
Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted
with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability**

***Deliverable 1.2
Database populated with European diversification experiences***

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PU Public	X
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1 Introduction

The EU Horizon 2020 project DiverIMPACTS aims to promote the realisation of the full potential of crop diversification through rotation, multicropping and intercropping by demonstrating technical, economic and environmental benefits for farmers, along the value chain and for society at large, and by providing innovations that can remove existing barriers and lock-ins of practical diffusion.

DiverIMPACTS does so by combining findings from several participatory case studies with a set of field experiments across Europe, and translating these into strategies, recommendations and fit-for-purpose tools developed with and for farmers, advisors and other actors along the value chain.

To first gain a good overview of the current situation, i.e. the existing success stories and challenges of crop diversification in Europe, Work Package 1 (WP 1) identified and analysed factors of success and failure associated with a variety of crop diversification experiences (CDEs) outside those already represented in the consortium (see Deliverable 1.1). WP 1 thus makes sure that the rich experience with crop diversification initiatives across Europe (e.g.

from other Horizon 2020 projects) is taken into account for developing strategies, recommendations and tools.

Deliverable 1.1 provided i) a list of key drivers (ex ante occurrence of market opportunities, environmental constraints, availability of enabling advisory services, land and workforce availability etc.) to be further considered in WP3, and WP5; and ii) a comprehensive and exhaustive description of the links between key factors and CDE types. This analysis is the basis for consolidating or updating the tentative typology of crop diversification situations used for setting up DiverIMPACTS (case studies), and was used for selecting experiences for more detailed investigations in T1.2. It also complements the identification and characterisation of lock-ins and barriers to crop diversification, and serves their overcoming. During the process of collecting, cleaning and analysing the survey data, a Database of European diversification experiences was created.

2 Results

All together 128 valid responses from 15 European countries – mainly from the project countries Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Sweden, Switzerland, and UK, but also from Denmark, Finland, Luxemburg and Spain were received in T1.1, and were included in the database.

The database is stored in original and back-up form in a tabular '.csv' format that can be opened in Excel on the Sharepoint system of the project, under restricted WP1 area. A further '.csv' file was created to store the metadata of the database. This file helps to have a better overview of the questions and sub-questions that were asked in the survey and the type of answer that could be provided to each of them (e.g. factor, Yes-No selection or character).

Using the meta data and the database, a selection of personal data fields has been made (e.g. email addresses and names of people) that cannot be published with open access, and needs special attention and data handling. These variables were removed from the original database, and a public version of the database was created that can be shared with third parties. Links to the data files will be shared here after.

Developping a Shiny(c) application in R was chosen as a solution to visualize the public data, and make it possible for Partners and all interested parties to interactively view the survey results. The Shiny application is shared as an R-package and are freely accessible on the internet. The users have the possibility to download application and public data in order to visualize them on their own computer. A remote solution, facilitating the consultation of the data, will be installed in CRA-W, where the open data analyses module will be hosted. A short user guide and tutorial is part of this deliverable for helping interested parties to use the Shiny interface.

The chosen approach, linking R scripts, R packages and data files, will be useful in the future in order to continuously complete the data base and to update the application (new graphs, new functions regarding the demand of the main users). The release of the application will be shared using modern technologies of information and communication : project website, newsletter, blogs, twitter and other social networks.

3 Partners involved in the work

Task leader is Dóra Drexler (ÖMKI). She coordinated the survey and its statistical analysis. WP leader is Frédéric Vanwindekens (CRA-W). He contributed to the writing of the metadata document, the screening of the data entries for sensitive data and the programming of the R script. He also worked on the visualization of the public database in shiny application. Didier Stilmant (CRA-W) and Antoine Messéan (INRA) contributed with consultations and coordination during the work period. The database was populated with cases by the Project Partners, as detailed in Deliverable 1.1.

4 How to consult the data base on crop diversification experiences accross Europe and how to use the 'surveyvisualizr' for the data

This part of the deliverable is a tutorial for (i) having access to the data base, and if needed (ii) configuring your computer and using the application for consulting the data collecting during the first survey of the WP1 of the project DiverIMPACTS.

The application is running on R through a ShinyAPP via the R-package `surveyvisualizr`.

The goal of `surveyvisualizr` is to visualize data collected from surveys. This package is working in R and is completed by a shiny app. You will need a recent version of R. If you don't have any experience or preference, Rstudio can help you for starting (code editor). This package is in development and accessible on Gitlab.

4.1 The data base

4.1.1 The meta-data

The meta-data linked to this survey are public. It is published on the survey-public-data repository : `survey_438634_meta_data.csv`. It is shared as a 'csv' file. The fields that can be consulted are the following ones ¹

"full" The full question asked in the survey

"name" The code (id) of the variable in the data-base (a question, a sub-question of an item of a question)

"big.questions" The code (id) of a main question. Can be shared by different variables.

"big.questions.scales" For some questions, two opposing scales are linked to a question. Code of this question can be found here.

"big.questions.scales.info" For some questions, two opposing scales are linked to a question. Information on the scales can be found here.

¹this table can be considered as the meta-data of the meta-data

"**main**" The main question (text) linked to a variable or different variables

"**item**" The sub-question or the item of a main question

"**class**" The class of the variable : numeric, factor, text.

"**levels**" The levels that can be found as answers for a factor variable

"**status.deliverable**" The status of the variable for this deliverable (public - restricted or to be confirmed).

For information, at the end of November 2018, there are **330** 'public' variables, **10** 'restricted' variables and **70** 'to be confirmed' variables.

The meta data were also edited in a table that is reproduced at Appendix B of this deliverable.

4.1.2 The classing of the data in order to determine their status

So far, the data of the first survey have been classed in three categories according to their internal characteristics and human check up. The Figure 1 presents the main criteria that have been used.

The classing of the variable is a continuous process that will aim to class the 'to be confirmed' variables as 'public' (mainly) or 'restricted'.

4.1.3 The public data

Lots of data collected during this survey are public (see here above). It is published on the repository : <http://gitrural.cra.wallonie.be/diverimpacts/survey-public-data>. Two '.csv' files were produced :

- `survey_438634_R_data_file.csv`. This file is better for the data analyses as the factor data are 'coded' (e.g. [1, 0] for [TRUE, FALSE]). It can be easily import using the 'R Script' in the folder (read-data-files.R). The script is produced by Limesurvey and add labels to variables (the text of the asked questions/items) and labels to levels of factors (the selected answers).
- `survey_438634_R_data_file-names.csv`. This file is better for 'human reading' as the factor data are reproduced as text in the data base, the same text selected in the survey by the interviewees. If needed, this file can be import using the 'R Script' in the folder (read-data-files-names.R).

The public data (open data) are also reproduced in the Appendix 3 of this deliverable, as tables. We used the `data_file-name` with more explicit answers.

4.1.4 The global data base

Some variables collected during the survey were considered as 'personal' data (names, ip adresses, emails, ...) and are therefore not part of this deliverable. These data were removed from the public data base in an anonymisation process. The full data base will not be shared outside of the DiverIMPACTS project.

Figure 1: Process for determining the status of the variables. Check needed is constituted mainly by 'comments' variables or free text linked to questions.

4.1.5 The to-be-confirmed data

A part of the variable could contain some personal information. They presently are considered as restricted data. A reviewing by WP-leaders and project coordinators is plan in order to class these last variables as public or restricted.

4.2 The application for visualizing the data

In this section, you will find a tutorial for setting your computer up and using the application. All the scripts of this section are already present in the files you will download.

4.2.1 Installation and setup

The functions and the scripts that will run 'surveyvisualizr' for DiverIMPACTS project is hosted here : <http://gitrural.cra.wallonie.be/diverimpacts/survey-app-data>. You can download the zip file `surveyviz_diverimpacts.zip` and unzip it on your computer. It will clone the repository ². In the 'diverIMPACTS' folder, you will find two main files : 'init.R' and 'setup.R'. For the first time, you will open 'setup.R' and source it in R (Rstudio, emacs, ...), or run line by line. It will mainly install on your computer the R libraries that are required for the application. The main command will install the package 'surveyvisualizr' in itself ³.

If you encounter some issues, you can contact me here.

4.2.2 Usage

After your computer is set up, you can open the 'init.R' file. Please change the **working directory** of R to the path of this file ⁴.

Source this file, or more safely run line by line. The various steps are :

1. Cleaning and loading libraries

```
rm(list=ls())

## Packages
## =====
library(surveyvisualizr)

library(tidyr)
library(dplyr)
library(shiny)
library(plotly)
library(DT)
library(RColorBrewer)
```

²if you know git, you can also use the git command : `git clone http://gitrural.cra.wallonie.be/diverimpacts/survey-app-data.git`

³hosted on Gitlab. Using the package 'devtools', you can install it with the command :
`devtools::install_git('https://gitlab.com/FrdVnW/surveyvisualizr', upgrade_dependencies = FALSE)`

⁴In RStudio, when the file is open : click Session > Set working directory > ... to source file location

2. Importing data The public data files are already in the 'data-raw' folder. So you can import directly these data.

```
source('R/load-di.R')
load.di()
```

If you have other data files, there are two possibilities :

- a) A - You have the two '*.csv' files, then :

```
##
## Copy the two data files :
## - survey_438634_R_data_file.csv
## - survey_438634_R_data_file-names.csv
## in the 'data-raw' folder of your working directory
## and run :
##
source('R/load-di.R')
load.di()
```

- b) B (easier) - You have a '*.RData' file, then :

```
##
## This file can be :
## - di_variables_public.RData
## - di_variables_tbc.RData (internal, contains public data)
## - di_variables_restricted.RData (internal, contains all data)
##
## Copy the file you have in the 'data-raw' folder of
## your working directory. Run one of the
## following command, depending of your file :
##
## load('./data-raw/di_variables_public.RData')
## load('./data-raw/di_variables_tbc.RData')
## load('./data-raw/di_variables_restricted.RData')
```

3. Launch the application You can launch the application with the following command.

```
## Launch the application
## =====
surveyvisualizr()
```

4.3 Hosting the application on a server

The application can be shared on server in order to facilitate its usage by a large public. First tries were made on the 'shinyapps.io' service and it is technically concluding. We are now evaluating the possibilities to have a secured and long term version of this kind of service. The link to the online application is : <https://craw.shinyapps.io/diverimpacts/>. We ask reader to use this link with parcimony as we have now a time-limited usage of this service.

4.4 Screencast : tutorial for the usage of the application

A screencast was produced in order to help partners of DiverIMPACTS and users of the application.

Survey visualizer

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Help | Plot | Table | Map | Report (full)

Welcome in the Survey visualizer app !

This app is there for visualising and reporting results of survey. This one is build for DiverIMPACTS EU-crop diversification in Europe. You will explore the results from the first survey on the diversity of Crop Diversification Experiences in Europe. Have a nice experience ! [THIS IS A WORK IN PROGRESS AND COMMENTS ARE WELCOME on my email]

[my email](#)

Getting start

The 4 output tabs

Beside this 'Help' tab, you will find plot, table, maps and report tab. You can navigate. Plot is the main tab can start there.

The left pannel : your choices

In the left pannel, you will be asked to select a main question. The app will select the best way to show : texts or bar plot mainly. If 'Other' or 'Comment' open fields are available for the selected question, you them on screen by selecting these two options. An important element is the 'criteria'. If no criteria is selected then plots are show for the whole respondent (all). If you select a criteria --which is question generate Y

Link to the screencast : <https://youtu.be/DkSa78KmH2Y>

Here are some other screenshots of the possibilities of the application :

Big question

Select the main question for which you want to analyze the answers

1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?

Free text, comments, 'other' fields :

Other field
 Comment field

Annotation on graph (only without comparison)

number

Position of bar plot for comparison

stack

First criteria (colors)

Big question or computed variable

No comparison or computed variables

Criteria

Regions of Europe

Question A5 :1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?

Criteria (color) eu.region :

Plot

Targeted Outcome	Western Europe	Southern Europe	Northern Europe	Eastern Europe
Improved environmental preservation	35	15	10	15
Improved crop production stability	25	15	10	15
Higher economic income	20	15	10	15
Lower input levels	15	10	10	10
New food product	15	10	10	10
Higher yield levels	15	10	10	10
Other	15	10	10	10
Better cash crop quality	15	10	10	10
New value chain	15	10	10	10
Landscape aesthetics	15	10	10	10
New industrial product (e.g. bioenergy carriers, biomaterials, biochemicals)	15	10	10	10
New feed product	15	10	10	10
Compliance to legal requirements	15	10	10	10
New production cooperative	15	10	10	10
New information support tools for professionals	15	10	10	10
New certification label	15	10	10	10

Regions of Europe: Western Europe (blue), Southern Europe (yellow), Northern Europe (green), Eastern Europe (orange)

Other and comments

No other fields with free text for this question
No comment for this question

DiverIMPACTS

Big question
 Select the main question for which you want to analyze the answers

1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?

Free text, comments, 'other' fields :

Other field
 Comment field

Annotation on graph (only without comparison)

number

Position of bar plot for comparison

fill

First criteria (colors)

Big question or computed variable

No comparison or computed variables

Criteria

Regions of Europe

Question A5 : 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?

Criteria (color) eu.region :

Plot

Other and comments

No other fields with free text for this question

No comment for this question

DiverIMPACTS

Big question
 Select the main question for which you want to analyze the answers

2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?

Free text, comments, 'other' fields :

Other field
 Comment field

Annotation on graph (only without comparison)

number

Position of bar plot for comparison

fill

Question B6 : 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?

Criteria (color) eu.region :

Plot

4.5 Licenses

Two kind of licenses are used in the framework of this deliverable :

4.5.1 Application and scripts : GPL-3

```
## THIS SCRIPT is a program for configuring and using
## the surveyvisualizr package in the framework of the
## DiverIMPACTS project
## Copyright (c) 2018 Frédéric Vanwindekens
## Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques
## Projet DiverIMPACTS
## License GPL-3
```

4.5.2 Open data : cc-by

```
## Copyright (c) 2018 Frédéric Vanwindekens, Dóra Drexler
## Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques (CRA-W)
## Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (ÖMKi),
## Projet DiverIMPACTS (https://www.diverimpacts.net/)
## License cc-by
```

5 Conclusions

Task 1.1 was based on a well-structured online survey, which was conducted between January and April 2018. All together 128 valid responses were received from 15 European countries to this questionnaire. The online survey was developed and published with the programme LimeSurvey. The survey was well-structured and included 72 questions and sub-questions. The responses to the survey were gathered in an on-line database of Limesurvey, and were later on exported in csv format to the repository of ÖMKI. The original database was cleaned and checked for sensitive data after the completion of the survey. Besides the full database a public database of European Crop Diversification Experiences was created, where all sensitive and personal data have been removed.

For helping interested experts and individuals to interactively investigate and visualize the public database, an R script was developed and the database was installed in a Shinyapp solution. This will be made available to the public through CRA-W as soon as it installs a shinyapp server within its institution. A metadata table (.csv) was created also to facilitate an easier overview of the database, and an R script was developed to help R users with data extraction.

6 Appendices

Lots of open source digital material are linked to this deliverable. Internet links and open access to scripts, files and application are provided in the main text here above.

The appendices are constituted by printed version of data files :

- **A. Metadata** of the Database of European Crop Diversification Initiatives. The open access '.csv' file link is provided in the deliverable.
- **B. Public Database** of European Crop Diversification Initiatives. The open access '.csv' file link is provided in the deliverable.

Appendix A : The meta data of the data base of the quantitative survey (task 1.1)

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November, 2018

Meta data

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
id	id	id	id	NA	id		numeric		public_no_problem
submitdate	submitdate	submitdate	submitdate	NA	submitdate		character		restricted
lastpage	lastpage	lastpage	lastpage	NA	lastpage		character		restricted
startlanguage	startlanguage	startlanguage	startlanguage	NA	startlanguage		character		restricted
token	token	token	token	NA	token		character		restricted
startdate	startdate	startdate	startdate	NA	startdate		character		restricted
datestamp	datestamp	datestamp	datestamp	NA	datestamp		character		restricted
ipaddr	ipaddr	ipaddr	ipaddr	NA	ipaddr		character		restricted
A1	1.1 Title/Name of diversification initiative	A1	A1	NA	1.1 Title/Name of diversification initiative		character		to_be_confirmed
A2_Sg001	[Country] 1.2 Geographical location of diversification initiative	A2_Sg001	A2	NA	1.2 Geographical location of diversification initiative	Country	character		public_no_problem
A2_Sg002	[Region(s)] 1.2 Geographical location of diversification initiative	A2_Sg002	A2	NA	1.2 Geographical location of diversification initiative	Region(s)	character		to_be_confirmed
A3_Sg001	[Rotation was applied (different crops in successive growing years) Please describe the typical plant order.] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_Sg001	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Rotation was applied (different crops in successive growing years) Please describe the typical plant order.	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A3_Sg001c	[Comment] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_Sg001cc	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A3_SG002	[Multicropping was applied (different crops within one growing year) Please describe the typical plant order.] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG002	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Multicropping was applied (different crops within one growing year) Please describe the typical plant order.	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A3_SG002c	[Comment] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG002cc	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A3_SG003	[Intercropping was applied (growing different species or cultivars in proximity in the same field) Please describe the typical intercropping (e.g. mixed, row or strip intercropping).] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG003	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Intercropping was applied (growing different species or cultivars in proximity in the same field) Please describe the typical intercropping (e.g. mixed, row or strip intercropping).	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A3_SG003c	[Comment] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG003cc	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A3_SG004	[None of these were applied] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG004	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	None of these were applied	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A3_SG004c	[Comment] 1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	A3_SG004cc	A3	NA	1.3 Please describe the production practice before the diversification initiative. Use the comment box to complete your answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A4_SG009	[New cash or cover crop(s) were included in the rotation (these could be annual or perennial)] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SG009	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	New cash or cover crop(s) were included in the rotation (these could be annual or perennial)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A4_SG009c	[Comment] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SG009cc	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A4_SQ010	[New cash or cover crop(s) were included within one season (multicropping)] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SQ010	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	New cash or cover crop(s) were included within one season (multicropping)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A4_SQ010c	[Comment] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SQ010cc	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A4_SQ008	[New crop mixture(s) were applied (intercropping)] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SQ008	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	New crop mixture(s) were applied (intercropping)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A4_SQ008c	[Comment] 1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	A4_SQ008cc	A4	NA	1.4 What is/was done? Please indicate in the comment box the starting date of the diversification initiative, and where possible, the end (Year). Please add this information before selecting the next relevant answer.	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A41	1.4.1 Please list which crops were included in the rotation	A41	A41	NA	1.4.1 Please list which crops were included in the rotation		character		to_be_confirmed
A42	1.4.2 Please indicate which cash or cover crop(s) were included within one season (multiple cropping).	A42	A42	NA	1.4.2 Please indicate which cash or cover crop(s) were included within one season (multiple cropping).		character		to_be_confirmed
A43_SQ001	[Which crops were sown?] 1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	A43_SQ001	A43	NA	1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	Which crops were sown?	character		to_be_confirmed
A43_SQ002	[Which was the main crop?] 1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	A43_SQ002	A43	NA	1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	Which was the main crop?	character		to_be_confirmed
A43_SQ003	[Which crops were harvested (grain/silage)?] 1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	A43_SQ003	A43	NA	1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	Which crops were harvested (grain/silage)?	character		to_be_confirmed
A43_SQ004	[What was the sowing design (mixed, alternated row, strip)?] 1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	A43_SQ004	A43	NA	1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	What was the sowing design (mixed, alternated row, strip)?	character		to_be_confirmed
A43_SQ005	[Was the usual sowing density of the crops modified?] 1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	A43_SQ005	A43	NA	1.4.3 Please describe shortly the applied new intercropping	Was the usual sowing density of the crops modified?	character		to_be_confirmed

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A5_SQ001	[New food product] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ001	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New food product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ002	[New feed product] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ002	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New feed product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ003	[New industrial product (e.g. bioenergy carriers, biomaterials, biochemicals)] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ003	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New industrial product (e.g. bioenergy carriers, biomaterials, biochemicals)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ004	[Improved crop production stability] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ004	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Improved crop production stability	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ005	[Better cash crop quality] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ005	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Better cash crop quality	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ015	[Higher yield levels] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ015	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Higher yield levels	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ014	[Lower input levels] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ014	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Lower input levels	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ013	[Higher economic income] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ013	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Higher economic income	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ006	[Improved environmental preservation] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ006	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Improved environmental preservation	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ007	[Landscape aesthetics] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ007	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Landscape aesthetics	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ008	[New value chain] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ008	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New value chain	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ009	[New certification label] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ009	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New certification label	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ010	[New production cooperative] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ010	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New production cooperative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ011	[Compliance to legal requirements] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ011	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Compliance to legal requirements	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ012	[New information support tools for professionals] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ012	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	New information support tools for professionals	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5_SQ016	[Other] 1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	A5_SQ016	A5	NA	1.5 What is/was the targeted outcome of the initiative?	Other	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A5a_SQ000	[Targeted outcome] 1.5a You have selected 'Other' as a targeted outcome of your diversification initiative. Please specify what this targeted outcome is/was.	A5a_SQ000	A5a	NA	1.5a You have selected 'Other' as a targeted outcome of your diversification initiative. Please specify what this targeted outcome is/was.	Targeted outcome	character		to_be_confirmed
A6_SQ001	[Farmers] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ001	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Farmers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A6_SQ002	[Advisors] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ002	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Advisors	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ003	[Researchers] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ003	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Researchers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ004	[Commercial companies] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ004	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Commercial companies	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ005	[Consumers] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ005	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Consumers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ006	[Authorities] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ006	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Authorities	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ007	[Certification organizations (e.g. for organic farming)] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ007	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Certification organizations (e.g. for organic farming)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ008	[NGOs (non governmental organisations that represent civil society)] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ008	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	NGOs (non governmental organisations that represent civil society)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6_SQ099	[Other] 1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	A6_SQ099	A6	NA	1.6 Who is/was involved in the initiative?	Other	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A6a_SQ000	[Involved actors] 1.6a You have selected 'Other' for involved actors of your diversification initiative. Please specify who these actors are/were.	A6a_SQ000	A6a	NA	1.6a You have selected 'Other' for involved actors of your diversification initiative. Please specify who these actors are/were.	Involved actors	character		to_be_confirmed
A61_SQ001	[As individual farmer(s)] 1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	A61_SQ001	A61	NA	1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	As individual farmer(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A61_SQ002	[Through informal farmer group(s)] 1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	A61_SQ002	A61	NA	1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	Through informal farmer group(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A61_SQ003	[Through farmer association(s)] 1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	A61_SQ003	A61	NA	1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	Through farmer association(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A61_other	[Other] 1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	A61_other	A61	NA	1.6.1 How were farmers involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A62_SQ001	[As individual advisor(s)] 1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	A62_SQ001	A62	NA	1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	As individual advisor(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A62_SQ002	[Through (national or regional) state advisory service organization(s)] 1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	A62_SQ002	A62	NA	1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	Through (national or regional) state advisory service organization(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A62_SQ003	[Through private advisory service organization(s)] 1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	A62_SQ003	A62	NA	1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	Through private advisory service organization(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A62_other	[Other] 1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	A62_other	A62	NA	1.6.2 How were advisors involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A63_SQ001	[As individual researcher(s)] 1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	A63_SQ001	A63	NA	1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	As individual researcher(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A63_SQ002	[Through University] 1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	A63_SQ002	A63	NA	1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	Through University	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A63_SQ003	[Through state research organization(s)] 1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	A63_SQ003	A63	NA	1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	Through state research organization(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A63_SQ004	[Through private research organization(s)] 1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	A63_SQ004	A63	NA	1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	Through private research organization(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A63_other	[Other] 1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	A63_other	A63	NA	1.6.3 How were researchers involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		restricted
A64_SQ001	[Seed producer(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ001	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Seed producer(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ006	[Plant protection companie(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ006	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Plant protection companie(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ008	[Fertilizer producer(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ008	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Fertilizer producer(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ007	[Machine producer(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ007	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Machine producer(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ005	[Processor(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ005	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Processor(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ002	[Trader(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ002	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Trader(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_SQ003	[Retailer(s)] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_SQ003	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Retailer(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A64_other	[Other] 1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	A64_other	A64	NA	1.6.4 What kind of commercial companies were involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A65_SQ001	[Ministry] 1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	A65_SQ001	A65	NA	1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	Ministry	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A65_SQ004	[National authority] 1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	A65_SQ004	A65	NA	1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	National authority	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A65_SQ002	[Regional authority] 1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	A65_SQ002	A65	NA	1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	Regional authority	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A65_SQ003	[Local authority] 1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	A65_SQ003	A65	NA	1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	Local authority	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A65_other	[Other] 1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	A65_other	A65	NA	1.6.5 What kind of authorities were involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A66	1.6.6 What kind of certification organizations were involved in the diversification initiative? Please specify.	A66	A66	NA	1.6.6 What kind of certification organizations were involved in the diversification initiative? Please specify.		character		to_be_confirmed
A67_SQ001	[Consumer organizations] 1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	A67_SQ001	A67	NA	1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	Consumer organizations	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A67_SQ002	[Environmental organizations] 1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	A67_SQ002	A67	NA	1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	Environmental organizations	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A67_SQ003	[Farmer organizations] 1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	A67_SQ003	A67	NA	1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	Farmer organizations	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A67_other	[Other] 1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	A67_other	A67	NA	1.6.7 What kind of NGOs were involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A7	1.7 Were you involved?	A7	A7	NA	1.7 Were you involved?		factor	Yes-No	public_no_problem
A71_SQ001	[As a farmer] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ001	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As a farmer	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ002	[As an advisor] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ002	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As an advisor	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ003	[As a researcher] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ003	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As a researcher	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ004	[As a commercial company] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ004	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As a commercial company	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ005	[As a consumer] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ005	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As a consumer	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ006	[As an authority] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ006	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As an authority	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ007	[As a certification organization] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ007	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As a certification organization	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ008	[As an NGO] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ008	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	As an NGO	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A71_SQ000	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]] 1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	A71_SQ000	A71	NA	1.7.1 Please specify how you were involved.	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]]	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A8	1.8 Did you initiate the diversification initiative?	A8	A8	NA	1.8 Did you initiate the diversification initiative?		factor	Yes-No	public_no_problem
A8_other	[Other] 1.8 Did you initiate the diversification initiative?	A8_other	A8	NA	1.8 Did you initiate the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A9_SQ001	[Farmers] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ001	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Farmers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ002	[Advisors] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ002	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Advisors	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ003	[Researchers] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ003	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Researchers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ004	[Commercial companies] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ004	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Commercial companies	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A9_SQ005	[Consumers] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ005	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Consumers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ006	[Authorities] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ006	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Authorities	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ007	[Certification organizations (e.g. for organic farming)] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ007	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	Certification organizations (e.g. for organic farming)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ008	[NGOs (non governmental organisations that represent civil society)] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ008	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	NGOs (non governmental organisations that represent civil society)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A9_SQ0001	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]] 1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	A9_SQ0001	A9	NA	1.9 Who initiated the diversification initiative	(438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A10_SQ001	[On commercial farms, by farmer(s)/farmers association(s)] 1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	A10_SQ001	A10	NA	1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	On commercial farms, by farmer(s)/farmers association(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A10_SQ002	[On private trial plots, by commercial firm(s)] 1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	A10_SQ002	A10	NA	1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	On private trial plots, by commercial firm(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A10_SQ003	[At scientific institutions (research centre, university)] 1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	A10_SQ003	A10	NA	1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	At scientific institutions (research centre, university)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A10_other	[Other] 1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	A10_other	A10	NA	1.10 Where was the diversification first tested?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A11a_SQ00	[Arable cropping systems] 1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	A11a_SQ000	A11a	NA	1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	Arable cropping systems	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A11a_SQ00	[Vegetable cropping systems] 1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	A11a_SQ000	A11a	NA	1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	Vegetable cropping systems	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A11a_SQ00	[Arable cropping systems with animals] 1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	A11a_SQ000	A11a	NA	1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	Arable cropping systems with animals	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A11a_SQ00	[Vegetable cropping systems with animals] 1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	A11a_SQ000	A11a	NA	1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	Vegetable cropping systems with animals	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A11a_other	[Other] 1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	A11a_other	A11a	NA	1.11a What type(s) of farming systems were involved in the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A11	1.11 Was the crop diversification initiative conducted on certified organic area?	A11	A11	NA	1.11 Was the crop diversification initiative conducted on certified organic area?		factor	No, the area was not certified organic- No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied- Yes, the area was certified organic completely- Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	public_no_problem
A12_SQ001	[EU project(s). Please specify project name(s).] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ001	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	EU project(s). Please specify project name(s).	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A12_SQ001	[Comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ001c	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A12_SQ002	[National or regional project funding. Please specify project name(s).] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ002	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	National or regional project funding. Please specify project name(s).	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A12_SQ002	[Comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ002c	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A12_SQ003	[Commercial company funding. Please specify company name(s).] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ003	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Commercial company funding. Please specify company name(s).	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A12_SQ003	[Comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ003c	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A12_SQ004	[Private non-commercial funding. Please specify e.g. Foundation name(s).] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ004	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Private non-commercial funding. Please specify e.g. Foundation name(s).	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A12_SQ004	[Comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ004c	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A12_SQ005	[Self-funding. Please specify who contributed.] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ005	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Self-funding. Please specify who contributed.	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A12_SQ005	[Comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_SQ005c	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A12_other	[Other] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_other	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A12_otherc	[Other comment] 1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	A12_otherco	A12	NA	1.12 How is/was the initiative funded?	Other comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A13	1.13 What was the magnitude of funding dedicated to the initiative? (in total in Euro)	A13	A13	NA	1.13 What was the magnitude of funding dedicated to the initiative? (in total in Euro)		character		restricted
A14_SQ001	[Breeding] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ001	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Breeding	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ002	[Seed production] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ002	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Seed production	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ003	[Development of inputs needed for production] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ003	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Development of inputs needed for production	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ004	[Organization of inputs needed for production] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ004	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Organization of inputs needed for production	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ005	[Machinery development] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ005	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Machinery development	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ006	[Organization of machinery needed for production] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ006	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Organization of machinery needed for production	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A14_SQ008	[Other] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ008	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	Other	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14_SQ077	[None] 1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	A14_SQ077	A14	NA	1.14 Did the diversification initiative include the following upstream value chain levels (levels that supply agricultural production)?	None	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A14a_SQ000	[Upstream value chain level] 1.4a You have selected 'Other' as an upstream value chain level that was included in your diversification initiative. Please specify what this upstream value chain level is/was.	A14a_SQ000	A14a	NA	1.4a You have selected 'Other' as an upstream value chain level that was included in your diversification initiative. Please specify what this upstream value chain level is/was.	Upstream value chain level	character		to_be_confirmed
A15_SQ001	[Quality assurance] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ001	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Quality assurance	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ002	[Transportation] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ002	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Transportation	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ003	[Logistics] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ003	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Logistics	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ004	[Processing] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ004	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Processing	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ005	[Marketing] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ005	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Marketing	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ006	[Sales] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ006	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Sales	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ008	[Other] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ008	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	Other	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A15_SQ077	[None] 1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	A15_SQ077	A15	NA	1.15 Did the initiative include the following down stream value chain levels (levels that come after primary production)?	None	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A15a_SQ00	[Downstream value chain level] 1.5a You have selected 'Other' as a downstream value chain level that was included in your diversification initiative. Please specify what this downstream value chain level is/was.	A15a_SQ00	A15a	NA	1.5a You have selected 'Other' as a downstream value chain level that was included in your diversification initiative. Please specify what this downstream value chain level is/was.	Downstream value chain level	character		to_be_confirmed
A16_SQ001	[Internal communication among participants (e.g. sharing experiences) (please specify communication tools)] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ001	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Internal communication among participants (e.g. sharing experiences) (please specify communication tools)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A16_SQ001	[Comment] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ001c	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A16_SQ002	[External communication for professionals (e.g. publishing results) (please specify communication tools)] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ002	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	External communication for professionals (e.g. publishing results) (please specify communication tools)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A16_SQ002	[Comment] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ002c	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A16_SQ003	[External communication for the public (e.g. media appearances) (please specify communication tools)] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ003	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	External communication for the public (e.g. media appearances) (please specify communication tools)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
A16_SQ003	[Comment] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_SQ003c	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A16_other	[Other] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_other	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Other	character		public_no_problem
A16_otherc	[Other comment] 1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	A16_otherc	A16	NA	1.16 What kind of communication approaches were used during the diversification initiative?	Other comment	character		to_be_confirmed
A17	1.17 Did the initiative use a specific co-innovation methodology? If so, please specify.	A17	A17	NA	1.17 Did the initiative use a specific co-innovation methodology? If so, please specify.		character		to_be_confirmed
A18_SQ001	[Website(s)] 1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	A18_SQ001	A18	NA	1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	Website(s)	character		to_be_confirmed
A18_SQ002	[Publication(s)] 1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	A18_SQ002	A18	NA	1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	Publication(s)	character		to_be_confirmed

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
A18_SQ003	[Video(s)] 1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	A18_SQ003	A18	NA	1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	Video(s)	character		to_be_confirmed
A18_SQ005	[Other] 1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	A18_SQ005	A18	NA	1.18 Where can we learn more about the initiative?	Other	character		to_be_confirmed
B1_SQ001	[The diversification initiative was] 2.1 In your opinion is/was the diversification initiative successful?	B1_SQ001	B1	NA	2.1 In your opinion is/was the diversification initiative successful?	The diversification initiative was	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ001	[New food product] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ001	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New food product	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ002	[New feed product] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ002	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New feed product	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ003	[New industrial product (e.g. bioenergy carriers, biomaterials, biochemicals)] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ003	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New industrial product (e.g. bioenergy carriers, biomaterials, biochemicals)	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B2_SQ004	[Improved crop production stability] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ004	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Improved crop production stability	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ005	[Better cash crop quality] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ005	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Better cash crop quality	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ015	[Higher yield levels] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ015	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Higher yield levels	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ014	[Lower input levels] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ014	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Lower input levels	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ013	[Higher economic income] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ013	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Higher economic income	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm successful	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B2_SQ006	[Improved environmental preservation] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ006	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Improved environmental preservation	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ007	[Landscape aesthetics] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ007	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Landscape aesthetics	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ008	[New value chain] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ008	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New value chain	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ009	[New certification label] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ009	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New certification label	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ010	[New production cooperative] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ010	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New production cooperative	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm overwhelm success- ful	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B2_SQ011	[Compliance to legal requirements] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ011	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	Compliance to legal requirements	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ012	[New information support tools for professionals] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ012	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	New information support tools for professionals	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B2_SQ0001	[[438634X176X2718SQ0001.shown]] 2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	B2_SQ0001	B2	NA	2.2 How successful is/was the realization of the diversification initiative's targeted outcomes?	{438634X176X2718SQ	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ001	[Breeding] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ001	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Breeding	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ002	[Seed production] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ002	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Seed production	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B3_SQ003	[Development of inputs needed for production] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ003	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Development of inputs needed for production	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ004	[Organization of inputs needed for production] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ004	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Organization of inputs needed for production	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ005	[Machinery development] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ005	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Machinery development	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ006	[Organization of machinery needed for production] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ006	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	Organization of machinery needed for production	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B3_SQ008	[[438634X176X2820SQ0001.shown]] 2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	B3_SQ008	B3	NA	2.3 Was the (re-)organization of upstream value chain levels (levels supplying primary production) successful?	{438634X176X2820SQ	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B4_SQ01	[Quality assurance] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ01	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Quality assurance	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B4_SQ02	[Transportation] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ02	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Transportation	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B4_SQ03	[Logistics] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ03	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Logistics	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B4_SQ04	[Processing] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ04	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Processing	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem
B4_SQ05	[Marketing] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ05	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Marketing	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelmir success- ful	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B4_SQ06	[Sales] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ06	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	Sales	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B4_SQ08	[[438634X176X2831SQ0002.shown]] 2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	B4_SQ08	B4	NA	2.4 Was the (re-)organization of downstream value chain levels (levels after primary production) successful?	{438634X176X2831SQ	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B5_SQ001	[Internal communication among participants (e.g. sharing experiences)] 2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	B5_SQ001	B5	NA	2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	Internal communication among participants (e.g. sharing experiences)	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B5_SQ002	[External communication for professionals (e.g. publishing results)] 2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	B5_SQ002	B5	NA	2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	External communication for professionals (e.g. publishing results)	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm successful	public_no_problem
B5_SQ003	[External communication for the public (e.g. media appearances)] 2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	B5_SQ003	B5	NA	2.5 In your opinion, were the applied communication approaches successful?	External communication for the public (e.g. media appearances)	factor	not at all successful- slightly successful- moderately successful- successful- overwhelm successful	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_1#0	[Professional expertise of involved actors] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_1#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Professional expertise of involved actors	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_1#1	[Professional expertise of involved actors] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_1#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Professional expertise of involved actors	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_2#0	[Technical solutions/tools applied] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_2#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Technical solutions/tools applied	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_2#1	[Technical solutions/tools applied] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_2#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Technical solutions/tools applied	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_3#0	[Availability of inputs (including seeds)] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_3#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Availability of inputs (including seeds)	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_3#1	[Availability of inputs (including seeds)] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_3#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Availability of inputs (including seeds)	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_4#0	[Market conditions] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_4#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Market conditions	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_4#1	[Market conditions] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_4#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Market conditions	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_5#0	[Amount of financial resources committed] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_5#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Amount of financial resources committed	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_5#1	[Amount of financial resources committed] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_5#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Amount of financial resources committed	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_6#0	[Available timeframe of the initiative] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_6#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Available timeframe of the initiative	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_6#1	[Available timeframe of the initiative] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_6#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Available timeframe of the initiative	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_7#0	[Commitment of the involved actors] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_7#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Commitment of the involved actors	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_7#1	[Commitment of the involved actors] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_7#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Commitment of the involved actors	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_8#0	[Organization of actors within the diversification initiative] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_8#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Organization of actors within the diversification initiative	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_8#1	[Organization of actors within the diversification initiative] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_8#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Organization of actors within the diversification initiative	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_9#0	[Communication activities] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_9#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Communication activities	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_9#1	[Communication activities] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_9#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Communication activities	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_10#0	[General public interest] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_10#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	General public interest	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B6_10#1	[General public interest] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_10#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	General public interest	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_11#0	[Other] [Scale 1] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_11#0	B6	Failure	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Other	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B6_11#1	[Other] [Scale 2] 2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	B6_11#1	B6	Success	2.6 Which factors have contributed to the success respectively failure of your diversification initiative?	Other	factor	not contributed at all-slightly contributed-moderately contributed-strongly contributed-very strongly contributed	public_no_problem
B61	2.6.1 You have rated a factor contributing to the failure of the diversification initiative in the 'Other' category of question 2.6. Please specify what this factor is.	B61	B61	NA	2.6.1 You have rated a factor contributing to the failure of the diversification initiative in the 'Other' category of question 2.6. Please specify what this factor is.		character		to_be_confirmed
B62	2.6.1 You have rated a factor contributing to the success of the diversification initiative in the 'Other' category of question 2.6. Please specify what this factor is.	B62	B62	NA	2.6.1 You have rated a factor contributing to the success of the diversification initiative in the 'Other' category of question 2.6. Please specify what this factor is.		character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B63_SQ001	[Agronomic] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ001	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Agronomic	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ002	[Economic] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ002	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Economic	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ003	[Policy] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ003	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Policy	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ004	[Social sciences] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ004	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Social sciences	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ005	[Natural sciences] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ005	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Natural sciences	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ006	[Marketing] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ006	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Marketing	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ007	[Sales] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ007	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Sales	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_SQ008	[Communication] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_SQ008	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Communication	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63_other	[Other] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63_other	B63	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Other	character		public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B64	2.6.4 You have rated technical solutions/tools applied as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which tools were/are most relevant in your case?	B64	B64	NA	2.6.4 You have rated technical solutions/tools applied as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which tools were/are most relevant in your case?		character		to_be_confirmed
B65_SQ001	[Seeds] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_SQ001	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Seeds	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65_SQ002	[Fertilizers] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_SQ002	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Fertilizers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65_SQ003	[Herbicides] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_SQ003	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Herbicides	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65_SQ004	[Pesticides] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_SQ004	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Pesticides	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65_SQ005	[Plant growth promoters] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_SQ005	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Plant growth promoters	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65_other	[Other] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65_other	B65	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Other	numeric		public_no_problem
B66	2.6.6 You have rated market conditions as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify what were/are the most relevant conditions in your case?	B66	B66	NA	2.6.6 You have rated market conditions as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify what were/are the most relevant conditions in your case?		character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B67	2.6.7 You have rated committed financial resources as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the funding influenced your initiative?	B67	B67	NA	2.6.7 You have rated committed financial resources as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the funding influenced your initiative?		character		to_be_confirmed
B68_SQ001	[Farmers] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ001	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Farmers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ002	[Advisors] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ002	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Advisors	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ003	[Researchers] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ003	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Researchers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ004	[Commercial companies] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ004	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Commercial companies	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B68_SQ005	[Consumers] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ005	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Consumers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ006	[Authorities] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ006	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Authorities	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ007	[Certification organizations] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ007	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	Certification organizations	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ008	[NGOs] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ008	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	NGOs	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B68_SQ000	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]] 2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	B68_SQ000	B68	NA	2.6.8 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of involved actors.	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]]	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B610	2.6.10 You have rated internal organization of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the actors were organized?	B610	B610	NA	2.6.10 You have rated internal organization of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the actors were organized?		character		to_be_confirmed
B611	2.6.11 You have rated general public interest as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify in what way it influenced your initiative?	B611	B611	NA	2.6.11 You have rated general public interest as a relevant factor contributing to the failure of your diversification initiative. Please specify in what way it influenced your initiative?		character		to_be_confirmed
B63s_SQ00	[Agronomic] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Agronomic	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Economic] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Economic	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Policy] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Policy	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Social sciences] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Social sciences	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Natural sciences] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Natural sciences	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Marketing] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Marketing	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_SQ00	[Sales] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Sales	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B63s_SQ00:	[Communication] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_SQ00:	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Communication	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B63s_other	[Other] 2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	B63s_other	B63s	NA	2.6.3 You have rated professional expertise of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which expertise is/was most relevant?	Other	character		public_no_problem
B64s	2.6.4 You have rated technical solutions/tools applied as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which tools were/are most relevant in your case?	B64s	B64s	NA	2.6.4 You have rated technical solutions/tools applied as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which tools were/are most relevant in your case?		character		to_be_confirmed
B65s_SQ00:	[Seeds] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_SQ00:	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Seeds	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65s_SQ00:	[Fertilizers] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_SQ00:	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Fertilizers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65s_SQ00:	[Herbicides] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_SQ00:	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Herbicides	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65s_SQ00:	[Pesticides] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_SQ00:	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Pesticides	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
B65s_SQ00:	[Plant growth promoters] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_SQ00:	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Plant growth promoters	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B65s_other	[Other] 2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	B65s_other	B65s	NA	2.6.5 You have rated availability of inputs (including seeds) as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify which input availabilities were most relevant in your case?	Other	character		public_no_problem
B66s	2.6.6 You have rated market conditions as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify what were/are the most relevant conditions in your case?	B66s	B66s	NA	2.6.6 You have rated market conditions as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify what were/are the most relevant conditions in your case?		character		to_be_confirmed
B67s	2.6.7 You have rated committed financial resources as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the funding influenced your initiative?	B67s	B67s	NA	2.6.7 You have rated committed financial resources as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the funding influenced your initiative?		character		to_be_confirmed
B69_SQ001	[Farmers] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ001	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Farmers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmi committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ002	[Advisors] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ002	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Advisors	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmi committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ003	[Researchers] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ003	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Researchers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmi committed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B69_SQ004	[Commercial companies] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ004	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Commercial companies	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ005	[Consumers] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ005	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Consumers	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ006	[Authorities] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ006	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Authorities	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ007	[Certification organizations] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ007	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	Certification organizations	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B69_SQ008	[NGOs] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ008	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	NGOs	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
B69_SQ000	[[438634X176X2730SQ0001.shown]] 2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	B69_SQ000	B69	NA	2.6.9 You have rated commitment of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please indicate the commitment of participants.	(438634X176X2730SQ0001)	factor	Not at all committed- Slightly committed- Moderately committed- Very committed- Overwhelmingly committed	public_no_problem
B610s	2.6.10 You have rated internal organization of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the actors were organized?	B610s	B610s	NA	2.6.10 You have rated internal organization of involved actors as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify how the actors were organized?		character		to_be_confirmed
B611s	2.6.11 You have rated general public interest as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify in what way it influenced your initiative?	B611s	B611s	NA	2.6.11 You have rated general public interest as a relevant factor contributing to the success of your diversification initiative. Please specify in what way it influenced your initiative?		character		to_be_confirmed
C1	In the following picture the main steps of the life cycle of a project are modelled. In which state is your crop diversification initiative? Please indicate the number corresponding to this state, a number between 1 and 9.	C1	C1	NA	In the following picture the main steps of the life cycle of a project are modelled. In which state is your crop diversification initiative? Please indicate the number corresponding to this state, a number between 1 and 9.		numeric		public_no_problem
C2_SQ002	[No, it remained the same (please type 0 in the comment box)] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ002	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	No, it remained the same (please type 0 in the comment box)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C2_SQ002c	[Comment] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ002cc	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
C2_SQ003	[Yes, it increased by app. ... % (please specify)] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ003	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	Yes, it increased by app. ... % (please specify)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C2_SQ003c	[Comment] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ003cc	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed
C2_SQ004	[Yes, it decreased by app. ... % (please specify)] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ004	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	Yes, it decreased by app. ... % (please specify)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C2_SQ004c	[Comment] 3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	C2_SQ004cc	C2	NA	3.2 Did the size of the crop diversification area change during the lifetime of the diversification initiative?	Comment	character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C3_Sg001_1 [Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg001_1	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg001_2 [Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg001_2	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg001_3 [Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg001_3	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg002_1 [Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg002_1	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg002_2 [Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg002_2	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg002_3 [Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg002_3	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg003_1 [Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg003_1	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg003_2 [Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_Sg003_2	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms	character		to_be_confirmed

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C3_Sg003_	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ003_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg004_	[Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ004_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg004_	[Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ004_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg004_	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ004_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg005_	[Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ005_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg005_	[Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ005_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg005_	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ005_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)]	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_Sg006_	[Year] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SQ006_	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Year]	character		to_be_confirmed

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C3_SG006_1	[[Number of participating farms] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SG006_1	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Number of participating farms	character		to_be_confirmed
C3_SG006_2	[[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)] 3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	C3_SG006_2	C3	NA	3.3 How many farmers take/took part in the diversification initiative? Please specify the dynamics according to years. You may also define intervals, if the project was longer than six years.	[Approximate acreage of diversification initiative (ha)	character		to_be_confirmed
C4_1#0	[Agronomic (e.g. water availability)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_1#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Agronomic (e.g. water availability)	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_1#1	[Agronomic (e.g. water availability)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_1#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Agronomic (e.g. water availability)	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_2#0	[Economic (e.g. product price)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_2#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Economic (e.g. product price)	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_2#1	[Economic (e.g. product price)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_2#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Economic (e.g. product price)	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_3#0	[Public policy (e.g. regulations)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_3#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Public policy (e.g. regulations)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_3#1	[Public policy (e.g. regulations)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_3#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Public policy (e.g. regulations)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_4#0	[Personal interactions (e.g. team work)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_4#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Personal interactions (e.g. team work)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_4#1	[Personal interactions (e.g. team work)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_4#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Personal interactions (e.g. team work)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SQ001#	[Breeding (e.g. new varieties)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SQ001#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Breeding (e.g. new varieties)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SQ001#	[Breeding (e.g. new varieties)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SQ001#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Breeding (e.g. new varieties)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_SG002#	[Seed production (e.g. seed availability)] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG002#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Seed production (e.g. seed availability)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG002#	[Seed production (e.g. seed availability)] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG002#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Seed production (e.g. seed availability)	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG003#	[Development of inputs needed for production] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG003#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Development of inputs needed for production	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG003#	[Development of inputs needed for production] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG003#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Development of inputs needed for production	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG004#	[Organization of inputs needed for production] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG004#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Organization of inputs needed for production	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG004#	[Organization of inputs needed for production] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG004#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Organization of inputs needed for production	factor	slightly relevant- moderately relevant- very relevant- overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_SG005#	[Machinery development] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG005#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Machinery development	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG005#	[Machinery development] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG005#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Machinery development	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG006#	[Organization of machinery needed for production] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG006#	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Organization of machinery needed for production	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG006#	[Organization of machinery needed for production] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG006#	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Organization of machinery needed for production	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG01#0	[Quality assurance] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG01#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Quality assurance	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG01#1	[Quality assurance] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG01#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Quality assurance	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_SG02#0	[Transportation] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG02#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Transportation	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG02#1	[Transportation] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG02#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Transportation	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG03#0	[Logistics] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG03#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Logistics	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG03#1	[Logistics] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG03#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Logistics	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG04#0	[Processing] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG04#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Processing	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG04#1	[Processing] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG04#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Processing	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_SG05#0	[Marketing] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG05#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Marketing	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG05#1	[Marketing] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG05#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Marketing	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG06#0	[Sales] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG06#0	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Sales	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG06#1	[Sales] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG06#1	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	Sales	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG0001	[[438634X176X2820SQ0001.shown]] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG0001	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	{438634X176X2820SQ	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SG0001	[[438634X176X2820SQ0001.shown]] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SG0001	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	{438634X176X2820SQ	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem

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	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C4_SQ0002	[[438634X176X2831SQ0002.shown]] [Scale 1] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SQ0002	C4	Drawbacks	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	(438634X176X2831SQ	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C4_SQ0002	[[438634X176X2831SQ0002.shown]] [Scale 2] 3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	C4_SQ0002	C4	Enablers	3.4 Did the diversification initiative encounter any drawbacks or enablers during its lifetime? Please rate the following potential drawbacks/enablers on both scales.	(438634X176X2831SQ	factor	slightly relevant-moderately relevant-very relevant-overwhelmir relevant	public_no_problem
C41_1	[Water availability (for irrigation)] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_1	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Water availability (for irrigation)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_2	[Crop protection] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_2	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Crop protection	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_3	[Weed management] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_3	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Weed management	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_4	[Soil type] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_4	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Soil type	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_5	[Climatic issues (e.g. drought)] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_5	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Climatic issues (e.g. drought)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_6	[Machinery] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_6	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Machinery	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C41_7	[Quality of agricultural product] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_7	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Quality of agricultural product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_8	[Yield of agricultural product] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_8	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Yield of agricultural product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_9	[Storage] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_9	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Storage	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_10	[Expertise available on diversification] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_10	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Expertise available on diversification	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_11	[Availability of new crop propagation materials] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_11	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Availability of new crop propagation materials	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_12	[Availability of inputs] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_12	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Availability of inputs	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41_other	[Other] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41_other	C41	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C42_1	[Low price of new product(s)] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_1	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Low price of new product(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42_2	[High cultivation costs] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_2	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	High cultivation costs	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C42_3	[Low yield] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_3	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Low yield	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42_4	[Higher risk of crop loss] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_4	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Higher risk of crop loss	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42_5	[Competition with mainstream producers] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_5	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Competition with mainstream producers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42_6	[Buyers' focus on single crops] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_6	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Buyers' focus on single crops	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42_other	[Other] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42_other	C42	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C43_1	[CAP Pillar I - Greening measure] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_1	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	CAP Pillar I - Greening measure	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43_2	[CAP Pillar II - Rural Development Program] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_2	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	CAP Pillar II - Rural Development Program	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43_3	[Nitrate Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_3	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Nitrate Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43_4	[Water Framework Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_4	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Water Framework Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43_7	[Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_7	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C43_6	[European Seed Law] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_6	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	European Seed Law	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43_other	[Other] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43_other	C43	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy drawbacks as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C44_1	[Knowledge exchange with the actors of the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_1	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Knowledge exchange with the actors of the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44_2	[Public interaction/participation (e.g. field days)] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_2	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Public interaction/participation (e.g. field days)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44_3	[New contacts established through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_3	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New contacts established through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44_4	[New cooperations established through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_4	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New cooperations established through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44_5	[New skills acquired through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_5	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New skills acquired through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44_other	[Other] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44_other	C44	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important drawbacks for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C41e_1	[Water availability (for irrigation)] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_1	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Water availability (for irrigation)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C41e_2	[Crop protection] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_2	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Crop protection	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_3	[Weed management] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_3	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Weed management	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_4	[Soil type] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_4	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Soil type	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_5	[Climatic issues (e.g. drought)] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_5	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Climatic issues (e.g. drought)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_6	[Machinery] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_6	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Machinery	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_7	[Quality of agricultural product] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_7	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Quality of agricultural product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_8	[Yield of agricultural product] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_8	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Yield of agricultural product	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_9	[Storage] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_9	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Storage	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_10	[Expertise available on diversification] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_10	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Expertise available on diversification	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C41e_11	[Availability of new crop propagation materials] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_11	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Availability of new crop propagation materials	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_12	[Availability of inputs] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_12	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Availability of inputs	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C41e_other	[Other] 3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	C41e_other	C41e	NA	3.4.1 You have evaluated agronomic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which agronomic parameters were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C42e_1	[Higher price of new product(s)] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_1	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Higher price of new product(s)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42e_2	[Lower cultivation costs] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_2	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Lower cultivation costs	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42e_3	[Higher yield] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_3	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Higher yield	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42e_4	[Lower risk of crop loss] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_4	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Lower risk of crop loss	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42e_5	[Better competition with mainstream producers] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_5	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Better competition with mainstream producers	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C42e_6	[Buyers' willingness to purchase mixed crops] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_6	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Buyers' willingness to purchase mixed crops	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C42e_other	[Other] 3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	C42e_other	C42e	NA	3.4.2 You have evaluated economic enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which economic parameters were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[CAP Pillar I - Greening measure] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG001	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	CAP Pillar I - Greening measure	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[CAP Pillar II - Rural Development Program] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG002	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	CAP Pillar II - Rural Development Program	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[Nitrate Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG003	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Nitrate Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[Water Framework Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG004	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Water Framework Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG005	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_SG00	[European Seed Law] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_SG006	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	European Seed Law	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C43e_other	[Other] 3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	C43e_other	C43e	NA	3.4.3 You have evaluated policy enablers as very important for your initiative. Please specify which policy instruments were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C44e_1	[Knowledge exchange with the actors of the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_1	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Knowledge exchange with the actors of the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44e_2	[Public interaction/participation (e.g. field days)] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_2	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Public interaction/participation (e.g. field days)	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem

(continued)

	Full questions	Variable code	Question code	Scales info	Main question	Subquestion	Answers class	Levels of factors	Status of the deliverable
C44e_3	[New contacts established through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_3	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New contacts established through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44e_4	[New cooperations established through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_4	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New cooperations established through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44e_5	[New skills acquired through the initiative] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_5	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	New skills acquired through the initiative	factor	Yes-Not selected	public_no_problem
C44e_other	[Other] 3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	C44e_other	C44e	NA	3.4.4 You have evaluated personal interactions as very important enablers for your initiative. Please specify which personal interactions were most important?	Other	character		public_no_problem
C5	3.5 Would you like to share anything else about this diversification initiative?	C5	C5	NA	3.5 Would you like to share anything else about this diversification initiative?		character		to_be_confirmed
C6	3.6 Thank you for participating in this survey! If you wish to receive the results of this research, please provide your email address where we can send you the final report.	C6	C6	NA	3.6 Thank you for participating in this survey! If you wish to receive the results of this research, please provide your email address where we can send you the final report.		character		restricted

Appendix B : The public data of the quantitative survey (task 1.1)

Frédéric Vanwindekens

Louise Legein

Drexler Dóra

Didier Stilmant

Antoine Messéan

November, 2018

(continued)

id	id.2	id.1	A2_SQ001	A3_SQ001	A3_SQ002	A3_SQ003	A3_SQ004	A4_SQ009	A4_SQ010	A4_SQ008	A5_SQ001	A5_SQ002	A5_SQ003	A5_SQ004	A5_SQ005
231	231	231	france	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected				
232	232	232	France	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
233	233	233	UK	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected				
235	235	235	France	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
236	236	236	France	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes
237	237	237	France	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
238	238	238	France	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected

(continued)

id	A5_SQ015	A5_SQ014	A5_SQ013	A5_SQ006	A5_SQ007	A5_SQ008	A5_SQ009	A5_SQ010	A5_SQ011	A5_SQ012	A5_SQ016	A6_SQ001	A6_SQ002	A6_SQ003	A6_SQ004
238	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected						

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id	A6_SQ005	A6_SQ006	A6_SQ007	A6_SQ008	A6_SQ009	A61_SQ001	A61_SQ002	A61_SQ003	A61_other	A62_SQ001	A62_SQ002	A62_SQ003	A62_other	A63_SQ001	A63_SQ002
18	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA					
19	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
21	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
22	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
30	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
26	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
31	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Seed companies and contractors	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
32	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
35	Not selected	Yes	Yes	organic union, pseudo CETA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA					
33	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
36	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
40	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
42	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Organized by Biofarm (Swiss Cooperative of organic farmers)	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected
43	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
44	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
45	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA
46	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
48	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
49	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
51	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	cultivation manager/agronomis (EM)	Not selected	Not selected
189	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes
55	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
56	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
60	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	GAL	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	informal, interpersonal	Yes	Not selected
61	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Feldtage, Maschinen-vorfürungen	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA
187	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA				
65	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
66	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
67	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
69	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
72	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes				
76	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected				
77	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
78	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
83	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
85	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	The farmers took part in courses etc and also hosted experiments, but wre not initiators.	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes
88	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA				
90	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
92	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
93	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes				

(continued)

id	A6_SQ005	A6_SQ006	A6_SQ007	A6_SQ008	A6_SQ009	A61_SQ001	A61_SQ002	A61_SQ003	A61_other	A62_SQ001	A62_SQ002	A62_SQ003	A62_other	A63_SQ001	A63_SQ002
95	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Sender: French salesman paid by the Walloon region	NA	NA				
96	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
98	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	technician working for a farmers' co-op. technicians working of the the Dolomiti Bellunesi National Park	NA	NA
99	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
100	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
103	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
104	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
105	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
106	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
107	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
110	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
112	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	farmers' co-op	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	farmers' co-op	Not selected	Yes				
117	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	farmers' co-op	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	technicians from the farmers' co-op	Not selected	Yes				
120	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected
127	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
128	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
129	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
130	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA
131	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
132	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
134	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes				
137	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
138	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
140	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
141	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	They are members of the cooperative	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	As technicians of the Cooperative	NA	NA				
142	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes
143	Not selected	Yes	farmers that are members of the consortium COVALM (Horticulture Consortium of Marche valleys)	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes						
145	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected
149	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
151	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
154	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes
155	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes
156	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected				
157	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
159	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
160	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
164	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA				

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id	A6_SQ005	A6_SQ006	A6_SQ007	A6_SQ008	A6_SQ009	A61_SQ001	A61_SQ002	A61_SQ003	A61_other	A62_SQ001	A62_SQ002	A62_SQ003	A62_other	A63_SQ001	A63_SQ002
165	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected				
167	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
168	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
170	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
171	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
173	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
174	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
175	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
176	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA					
177	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
178	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes
179	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
180	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
181	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
182	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
192	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
193	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Chambre d'agriculture	Not selected	Yes
198	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
200	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
201	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	One of the ways to comply with the ecological EU rules	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
207	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes				
211	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
212	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
213	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
215	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
216	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Cooperative, Agricultural Development Group	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Agricultural Development Group	Not selected	Not selected
217	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes
220	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected
222	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	1 farmers (who is also within the supply chain- Baker)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
223	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Cooperative Through Cooperative Qualisol staff	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Cooperative	NA	NA					
224	Not selected	Cooperative Through Cooperative Qualisol staff	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected							
225	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected
226	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	informal group as become a formal group "Chavre Avenir" (status "association loi 1901") in 2010 and a commercial entity (SAS) with 6 farmers later on	Not selected	Yes	Yes	consultant who has been a subcontractor for the study of feasibility 'Construire en chanvre' (to build with hemp)	NA	NA

(continued)

id	A6_SQ005	A6_SQ006	A6_SQ007	A6_SQ008	A6_SQ009	A61_SQ001	A61_SQ002	A61_SQ003	A61_other	A62_SQ001	A62_SQ002	A62_SQ003	A62_other	A63_SQ001	A63_SQ002
227	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	demonstration platforms	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	technicians of the farm cooperative entity (groupe QUALISOL)	Not selected	Not selected
228	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected				
230	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected				
231	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
232	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
233	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA				
235	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	first informal groups, then they buy commun material for direct sowing	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	advisor from the Technical Agricultural Institut (Terres Inovia) with a convention	NA	NA
236	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	At first some individus and then farmers' groups	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Mixed based technical institute (UNIP et Terres Inovia)	Not selected	Not selected				
237	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA
238	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	at first individual contacts, and then 50 farmers have set up an association for concertation and negotiations facing the client	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA

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id	A63_SQ003	A63_SQ004	A64_SQ001	A64_SQ006	A64_SQ008	A64_SQ007	A64_SQ005	A64_SQ002	A64_SQ003	A64_other	A65_SQ001	A65_SQ004	A65_SQ002	A65_SQ003	A65_other
18	NA	NA	Not selected	Water-suppliers	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
19	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA									
21	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA									
22	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA									
30	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
26	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
31	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Contractors	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
32	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
36	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA				
40	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
42	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Sativa (Seed production and distribution company)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
44	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
45	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA					
46	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
48	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
49	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
51	Yes	Not selected	Land and Farm Men as processors, traders, advisors	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA							
189	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA				
55	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
60	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	communal representatives								
61	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Nordic Sugar	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
187	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
72	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
76	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
78	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
85	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA							
88	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
90	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA								
93	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
95	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
100	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
103	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
104	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
105	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
106	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
109	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA							
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									

(continued)

id	A63_SQ003	A63_SQ004	A64_SQ001	A64_SQ006	A64_SQ008	A64_SQ007	A64_SQ005	A64_SQ002	A64_SQ003	A64_other	A65_SQ001	A65_SQ004	A65_SQ002	A65_SQ003	A65_other
112	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
117	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
120	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
127	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA									
128	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
129	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA							
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
131	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
132	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
134	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	The private sector was able to fill the empty space left by the technical part of the public sector. In particular, in our initiative, some meetings with companies specialized in biofumigation were organized	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	ARSSA (Regional Agency for Agricultural Development Services), but only at the beginning of the initiative, then it was totally absent				
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
141	NA	NA	Not selected	Cooperatives belonging to our Casalasco Consortium (https://www.casalasco.it) for the auto-processing of pea and tomato; Barilla (https://www.barilla.it) for durum wheat logistic: harvest and transportation	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
142	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA								
143	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA					
145	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA
149	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
151	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
154	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
155	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA							
156	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
157	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
160	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA									
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
166	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
169	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
173	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									

(continued)

id	A63_SQ003	A63_SQ004	A64_SQ001	A64_SQ006	A64_SQ008	A64_SQ007	A64_SQ005	A64_SQ002	A64_SQ003	A64_other	A65_SQ001	A65_SQ004	A65_SQ002	A65_SQ003	A65_other
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
176	NA	NA	Not selected	Innovation and retail	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
177	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA
178	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
179	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA					
181	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
192	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
193	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA					
198	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
201	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA									
202	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Seed producer : as a customer and not as a supplier	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
207	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
213	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
215	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
216	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Feed manufacturer	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
217	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
220	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
224	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
225	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	industrials	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
226	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	for the defibering cooperative group QUALISOL	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
227	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
229	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
231	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
232	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
235	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									
236	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	A company which ensure storage and processing farmers' cooperative Val de Gascogne	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA									

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id	A67_SQ001	A67_SQ002	A67_SQ003	A67_other	A7	A71_SQ001	A71_SQ002	A71_SQ003	A71_SQ004	A71_SQ005	A71_SQ006	A71_SQ007	A71_SQ008	A71_SQ0001	A8
18	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
32	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	No						
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
36	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes				
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	Yes
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
189	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA				
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes						
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes						
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
78	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	No							
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
88	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	No						
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
92	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes						
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
95	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
100	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	No
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes						
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	No						
112	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
117	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
120	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Yes
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	No
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
129	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	No
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
132	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	No

(continued)

id	A67_SQ001	A67_SQ002	A67_SQ003	A67_other	A7	A71_SQ001	A71_SQ002	A71_SQ003	A71_SQ004	A71_SQ005	A71_SQ006	A71_SQ007	A71_SQ008	A71_SQ0001	A8
134	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
141	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes
142	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes
143	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes
145	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	No
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
154	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes					
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	No
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
157	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	Yes
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes						
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
167	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Ekoland: Asociacion og Organic Producers Ekoland in Poland	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes						
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes						
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
177	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Solidarność - social asociacion	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes						
178	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
181	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
192	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
193	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	No						
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
213	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	No
216	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
217	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes
220	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	Yes
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes							
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes						
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	No
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No

(continued)

id	A67_SQ001	A67_SQ002	A67_SQ003	A67_other	A7	A71_SQ001	A71_SQ002	A71_SQ003	A71_SQ004	A71_SQ005	A71_SQ006	A71_SQ007	A71_SQ008	A71_SQ0001	A8
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	No
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
235	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	No
236	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	No

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id	A8_other	A9_SQ001	A9_SQ002	A9_SQ003	A9_SQ004	A9_SQ005	A9_SQ006	A9_SQ007	A9_SQ008	A9_SQ0001	A10_SQ001	A10_SQ002	A10_SQ003	A10_other	A11a_SQ001
18	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
21	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
22	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
35	NA	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected						
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
36	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes								
40	Yes (on behalf of FiBL) and together with Bio Suisse	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes								
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
43	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	On a commercial farm, by the initiator	Yes
46	NA	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
49	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
189	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
60	not the initiator but rather the facilitator	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes								
61	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Versuchsfeld Werlte der Landwirtschaftskammer Niedersachsen	Yes
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	other farmer's experiences	Yes
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
78	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
83	NA	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected							
85	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
88	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	no test, rotation is the base for a good production, but becomes more difficult in specialised farmers. farmers experience	Yes						
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes

(continued)

id	A8_other	A9_SQ001	A9_SQ002	A9_SQ003	A9_SQ004	A9_SQ005	A9_SQ006	A9_SQ007	A9_SQ008	A9_SQ0001	A10_SQ001	A10_SQ002	A10_SQ003	A10_other	A11a_SQ001
92	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected								
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
95	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
98	yes as part Dolomiti Bellunesi National Park	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes								
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
100	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
105	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
106	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	regional experimental farms owned by the Regions	Yes
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
109	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
110	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected						
112	farmers' co-op	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes								
117	farmers' co-op	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected								
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
127	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Do not know	Yes
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
129	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	experimental farms belonging to the Regional authority	Yes
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
132	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
134	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Governmental organizations	Yes
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
141	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
142	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
143	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
145	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
154	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
155	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
160	Farmer	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes								
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	We included rotating staff and machinery with the crops	Not selected
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
169	NA	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes

(continued)

id	A8_other	A9_SQ001	A9_SQ002	A9_SQ003	A9_SQ004	A9_SQ005	A9_SQ006	A9_SQ007	A9_SQ008	A9_SQ0001	A10_SQ001	A10_SQ002	A10_SQ003	A10_other	A11a_SQ001
173	2013-2016	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected
177	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
179	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
180	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
181	as a partner of the program	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
193	father of the farmer	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
200	NA	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
201	European	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
202	Found Rules	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
213	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
215	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected
226	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
229	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
230	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	technical institute	Yes
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
232	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes
235	NA	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
236	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes
238	NA	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes

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id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
18	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
26	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
31	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Principally livestock with forage crops	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
36	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
40	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	x	NA	NA	NA	NA
42	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
43	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
46	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
49	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	pre-financing	NA	NA	NA	NA
189	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
55	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Livestock farming systems (South Wallonia)	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
61	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
187	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
66	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
67	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
69	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
70	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
72	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
76	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
77	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
78	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
83	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	Yes	Yes	Yes	collaboration between these different farm types	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
90	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
93	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
95	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Livestock farming	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
96	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
98	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
99	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
100	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
103	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected
104	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
105	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
106	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
107	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
110	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
112	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
117	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	arable: cereals - vegetables	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
120	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
127	Yes	Yes	Yes	All non-organic farms with more than 10 hectares of arable land.	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected
129	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	soybean in rotation too	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
130	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	from arable system to vegetable production system	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
131	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
132	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected
134	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
137	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	legumes	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	x	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes				
142	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
143	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes
145	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	wheat and malze are included but are not the main crops	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected
149	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
151	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
154	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
155	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
156	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
157	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic, but no pesticide and chemical fertilizers were applied	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
159	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
160	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
164	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
165	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
166	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
168	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected
169	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected
170	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
173	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
174	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
175	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
177	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	loans	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
178	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes
179	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
180	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
182	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
193	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
195	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
198	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
200	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
201	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
202	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
207	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
211	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
212	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
215	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected

(continued)

id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
216	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
217	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
220	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
222	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
224	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
226	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
227	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
228	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
231	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
232	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes
233	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
235	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes

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id	A11a_SQ002	A11a_SQ003	A11a_SQ004	A11a_other	A11	A12_SQ001	A12_SQ002	A12_SQ003	A12_SQ004	A12_SQ005	A12_other	A14_SQ001	A14_SQ002	A14_SQ003	A14_SQ004
236	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes, the area was certified organic completely	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
237	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	No, the area was not certified organic	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
238	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Both organic and non-organic areas were involved	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected

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id	A14_SQ005	A14_SQ006	A14_SQ008	A14_SQ077	A15_SQ01	A15_SQ02	A15_SQ03	A15_SQ04	A15_SQ05	A15_SQ06	A15_SQ08	A15_SQ77	A16_SQ001	A16_SQ002	A16_SQ003
238	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes						

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id	A16_other	B1_SQ001	B2_SQ001	B2_SQ002	B2_SQ003	B2_SQ004	B2_SQ005	B2_SQ015	B2_SQ014	B2_SQ013	B2_SQ006	B2_SQ007	B2_SQ008	B2_SQ009	B2_SQ010
18	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA
32	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	None	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	NA	slightly successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
40	Public	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA
42	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	not at all successful	successful	not at all successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	private for private purpose	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
49	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
189	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	NA
55	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
56	no communication	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
61	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA	NA
187	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA
66	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA
67	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	LEAF Demo farmer	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	LEAF Demonstration Farmers	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	not at all successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA
77	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	not at all successful	NA	NA
83	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
90	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful
93	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA

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id	A16_other	B1_SQ001	B2_SQ001	B2_SQ002	B2_SQ003	B2_SQ004	B2_SQ005	B2_SQ015	B2_SQ014	B2_SQ013	B2_SQ006	B2_SQ007	B2_SQ008	B2_SQ009	B2_SQ010
95	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	x	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA
98	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful
99	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	NA	NA
100	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful
103	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA
104	NA	slightly successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA						
105	x	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	slightly successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA
106	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
107	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
110	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	successful	successful
112	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	successful
117	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful
120	NA	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
127	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
129	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
130	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
131	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	slightly successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
132	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
134	NA	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	slightly successful	moderately successful	not at all successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful
137	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful
142	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	successful
143	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	successful
145	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA
149	NA	not at all successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
151	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA
154	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA
155	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA
157	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	not at all successful	NA
159	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA
160	NA	successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
165	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful

(continued)

id	A16_other	B1_SQ001	B2_SQ001	B2_SQ002	B2_SQ003	B2_SQ004	B2_SQ005	B2_SQ015	B2_SQ014	B2_SQ013	B2_SQ006	B2_SQ007	B2_SQ008	B2_SQ009	B2_SQ010
168	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA											
171	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA						
175	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
177	NA	slightly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful
178	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful
179	NA	slightly successful	successful	NA	NA	slightly successful	slightly successful	slightly successful	NA	slightly successful	successful	NA	slightly successful	successful	NA
180	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA
181	NA	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA
182	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA
193	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA
195	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful
198	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
200	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
201	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA
207	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	not at all successful	NA	slightly successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
211	None	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA
212	None	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA
215	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
216	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful
217	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA
220	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	Diver impacts	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	NA	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	slightly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA
225	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA
227	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA
228	none	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA
229	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	NA									
230	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA								
233	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	A16_other	B1_SQ001	B2_SQ001	B2_SQ002	B2_SQ003	B2_SQ004	B2_SQ005	B2_SQ015	B2_SQ014	B2_SQ013	B2_SQ006	B2_SQ007	B2_SQ008	B2_SQ009	B2_SQ010
236	NA	successful	not at all successful	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA
237	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA
238	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA

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id	B2_SQ011	B2_SQ012	B2_SQ001	B3_SQ001	B3_SQ002	B3_SQ003	B3_SQ004	B3_SQ005	B3_SQ006	B3_SQ008	B4_SQ01	B4_SQ02	B4_SQ03	B4_SQ04	B4_SQ05
18	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA
42	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	slightly successful	slightly successful	NA
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA
45	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	not at all successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA
189	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful
55	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	slightly successful	successful	successful
56	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	slightly successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful
61	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	slightly successful	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
66	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA
67	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	not at all successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful
72	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA
77	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	slightly successful
78	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful
82	NA	NA	NA	not at all successful	not at all successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	not at all successful
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
90	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA
92	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA
95	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful
100	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
103	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	slightly successful	NA

(continued)

id	B2_SQ011	B2_SQ012	B2_SQ001	B3_SQ001	B3_SQ002	B3_SQ003	B3_SQ004	B3_SQ005	B3_SQ006	B3_SQ008	B4_SQ01	B4_SQ02	B4_SQ03	B4_SQ04	B4_SQ05
104	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful							
105	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA						
106	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA							
107	NA	NA	successful	NA											
109	NA														
110	NA	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful										
112	NA	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful
117	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA
120	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
127	successful	NA													
128	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	slightly successful	slightly successful	moderately successful
129	NA	moderately successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA
132	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	slightly successful	NA
134	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	moderately successful
137	moderately successful	NA													
138	NA														
140	NA														
141	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful
142	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	slightly successful							
143	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful
145	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful
149	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	slightly successful	NA									
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful
154	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful				
155	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA						
156	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA						
157	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful
159	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	NA
164	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful										
165	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA						
166	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA									
167	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	slightly successful	overwhelmingly successful
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA								
170	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA									
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA
173	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA									
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA								
175	NA	slightly successful	NA												
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful

(continued)

id	B2_SQ011	B2_SQ012	B2_SQ001	B3_SQ001	B3_SQ002	B3_SQ003	B3_SQ004	B3_SQ005	B3_SQ006	B3_SQ008	B4_SQ01	B4_SQ02	B4_SQ03	B4_SQ04	B4_SQ05
177	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful				
178	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful									
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	NA														
181	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA
182	NA														
192	successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful				
193	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful				
195	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA
200	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA											
201	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	successful	successful	NA									
202	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA									
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA							
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	not at all successful	NA									
212	NA	NA	successful	NA											
213	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful
215	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA						
216	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful				
217	NA														
220	NA	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA						
222	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful						
223	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful
224	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful									
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA
226	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful
227	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	successful	slightly successful	slightly successful	successful	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful
228	NA	successful	successful												
229	NA														
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA									
231	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful
233	NA	successful	NA												
235	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	slightly successful	moderately successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
236	NA	NA	successful	not at all successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA
237	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA
238	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	successful	NA	successful	successful							

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id	B4_SQ06	B4_SQ08	B5_SQ001	B5_SQ002	B5_SQ003	B6_1#0	B6_1#1	B6_2#0	B6_2#1	B6_3#0	B6_3#1	B6_4#0	B6_4#1	B6_5#0	B6_5#1
18	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
19	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
21	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
22	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
30	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
26	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
31	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	successful	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	slightly contributed	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	very strongly contributed
32	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	not contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
35	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	at all NA	NA	NA
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
36	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
40	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
42	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
43	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
44	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	strongly contributed
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA
46	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed
48	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	strongly contributed	not contributed	not contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed
49	NA	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	at all NA	at all strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
51	NA	successful	successful	successful	successful	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed
189	successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed
55	successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	not contributed	NA	slightly contributed
60	slightly successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	at all NA	NA	very strongly contributed
61	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
187	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	not contributed
65	NA	slightly successful	successful	successful	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	at all very strongly contributed
66	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	slightly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	slightly contributed
76	NA	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	not contributed	NA	strongly contributed
78	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed

(continued)

id	B4_SQ06	B4_SQ08	B5_SQ001	B5_SQ002	B5_SQ003	B6_1#0	B6_1#1	B6_2#0	B6_2#1	B6_3#0	B6_3#1	B6_4#0	B6_4#1	B6_5#0	B6_5#1
82	not at all successful	NA	successful	slightly successful	not at all successful	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	slightly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	strongly contributed
83	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed
88	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	contributed strongly	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
90	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	contributed very strongly	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA
92	successful	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed
93	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	slightly contributed
95	NA	NA	successful	slightly successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
96	successful	successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
98	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
99	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed
100	NA	NA	successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed
103	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	contributed strongly	NA	NA	NA	contributed very strongly	NA	contributed strongly	NA	contributed NA
104	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	contributed very strongly	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	contributed strongly	NA	NA
105	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	successful	moderately successful	NA	contributed strongly	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	contributed NA	NA	strongly contributed
106	NA	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
107	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	contributed strongly	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed
110	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed
112	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	contributed strongly	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
117	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
120	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	moderately contributed
127	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	contributed NA	NA	NA	NA	contributed NA	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed
128	slightly successful	NA	moderately successful	successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed
129	NA	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed
130	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
131	moderately successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	contributed very strongly	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed
132	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	slightly contributed	contributed very strongly	moderately contributed	contributed NA	not contributed at all	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed
134	NA	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA
137	NA	NA	slightly successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed
140	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
141	moderately successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA
142	slightly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	NA	NA	contributed strongly	NA	NA	NA	contributed NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
143	successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	contributed strongly	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed
145	successful	NA	successful	NA	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
149	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	contributed NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed

(continued)

id	B4_SQ06	B4_SQ08	B5_SQ001	B5_SQ002	B5_SQ003	B6_1#0	B6_1#1	B6_2#0	B6_2#1	B6_3#0	B6_3#1	B6_4#0	B6_4#1	B6_5#0	B6_5#1
215	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed
216	moderately successful	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed
217	NA	NA	successful	successful	successful	NA	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	strongly contributed
220	NA	NA	NA	successful	successful	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed
222	moderately successful	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed
224	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA
225	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately successful	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA
226	overwhelmingly successful	NA	successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA
227	successful	NA	successful	NA	slightly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed
228	successful	NA	NA	NA	successful	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed
229	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	moderately contributed	moderately contributed
230	NA	NA	moderately successful	moderately successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA
231	NA	NA	successful	successful	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	successful	moderately successful	overwhelmingly successful	NA	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	successful	NA	NA	contributed NA	NA	contributed NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	contributed NA	NA	NA
235	NA	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	overwhelmingly successful	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
236	NA	NA	successful	NA	moderately successful	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	slightly contributed
237	successful	NA	successful	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	moderately contributed
238	successful	NA	successful	slightly successful	moderately successful	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	strongly contributed

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id	B6_6#0	B6_6#1	B6_7#0	B6_7#1	B6_8#0	B6_8#1	B6_9#0	B6_9#1	B6_10#0	B6_10#1	B6_11#0	B6_11#1	B63_SQ001	B63_SQ002	B63_SQ003
18	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	slightly contributed	very strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA
32	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected
40	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
42	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
45	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
46	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
189	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	slightly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	not contributed at all	NA	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
61	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
187	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
66	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
67	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	moderately contributed	slightly contributed	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	B6_6#0	B6_6#1	B6_7#0	B6_7#1	B6_8#0	B6_8#1	B6_9#0	B6_9#1	B6_10#0	B6_10#1	B6_11#0	B6_11#1	B63_SQ001	B63_SQ002	B63_SQ003
157	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
159	NA	slightly contributed	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	not contributed at all	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA
160	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	moderately contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	moderately contributed	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
177	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
178	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
179	moderately contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
193	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	not contributed at all	moderately contributed	not contributed at all	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
198	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
200	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
207	NA	NA	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
215	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
216	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
217	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
220	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	B6_6#0	B6_6#1	B6_7#0	B6_7#1	B6_8#0	B6_8#1	B6_9#0	B6_9#1	B6_10#0	B6_10#1	B6_11#0	B6_11#1	B63_SQ001	B63_SQ002	B63_SQ003
223	NA	slightly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	not contributed at all	not contributed at all	NA	NA	NA	NA
227	NA	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	very strongly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
228	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	slightly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	moderately contributed	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA
236	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	not contributed at all	NA	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	moderately contributed	NA	slightly contributed	moderately contributed	NA	NA	NA	NA
238	NA	NA	NA	very strongly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	NA	slightly contributed	NA	strongly contributed	strongly contributed	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected

(continued)

id	B63_SQ004	B63_SQ005	B63_SQ006	B63_SQ007	B63_SQ008	B63_other	B65_SQ001	B65_SQ002	B65_SQ003	B65_SQ004	B65_SQ005	B65_other	B68_SQ001	B68_SQ002	B68_SQ003
236	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
238	Not selected	need some expertise and need to take time : difficulties in protecting the crop growth and difficulties in harvesting in case you do not do it properly (need to be done carefully and slowly)	NA												

(continued)

id	B68_SQ004	B68_SQ005	B68_SQ006	B68_SQ007	B68_SQ008	B68_SQ0001	B63s_SQ001	B63s_SQ002	B63s_SQ003	B63s_SQ004	B63s_SQ005	B63s_SQ006	B63s_SQ007	B63s_SQ008	B63s_other
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
132	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA					
134	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA				
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	luck
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA
142	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA				
143	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
145	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
154	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
157	NA	Not at all committed	NA	NA	Not at all committed	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	machinery				
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
177	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	practice, internships taken abroad
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA					
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA					
181	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
193	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
202	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA					
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA					
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Biological sciences					
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA					
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	industrial processing				

(continued)

id	B68_SQ004	B68_SQ005	B68_SQ006	B68_SQ007	B68_SQ008	B68_SQ0001	B63s_SQ001	B63s_SQ002	B63s_SQ003	B63s_SQ004	B63s_SQ005	B63s_SQ006	B63s_SQ007	B63s_SQ008	B63s_other
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	commercial as the first and major type of expertise (outlets and markets)/ then public policy then economic expertise then agronomic skillness
228	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA					
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Evaluating phase shared with teh advisor						
236	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA						
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA

>

id	B65s_SQ001	B65s_SQ002	B65s_SQ003	B65s_SQ004	B65s_SQ005	B65s_other	B69_SQ001	B69_SQ002	B69_SQ003	B69_SQ004	B69_SQ005	B69_SQ006	B69_SQ007	B69_SQ008	B69_SQ0001
18	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
42	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Seeds being THE procondition	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
43	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Foil	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Slightly committed	Very committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA	Not at all committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
46	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	biological control inputs	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Slightly committed	Not at all committed	Not at all committed	NA	Not at all committed
189	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	fertilizing effect from the past due to livestock (well "greased")	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Not at all committed	NA	NA	Slightly committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
66	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not at all committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA
88	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	B65s_SQ001	B65s_SQ002	B65s_SQ003	B65s_SQ004	B65s_SQ005	B65s_other	B69_SQ001	B69_SQ002	B69_SQ003	B69_SQ004	B69_SQ005	B69_SQ006	B69_SQ007	B69_SQ008	B69_SQ0001
90	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed				
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed
99	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Moderately committed	NA							
100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA
103	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA
106	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
112	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
117	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
129	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Slightly committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA
130	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	organic pesticides	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
132	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	bacterial fertilizer	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA
134	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	Not selected	Cultivars with shorter cycle length in order to allow the multiple cropping	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA				
142	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Slightly committed	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	Slightly committed	Slightly committed
143	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Very committed	Slightly committed	NA	Slightly committed	NA	Slightly committed	Slightly committed
145	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	Slightly committed	Slightly committed	Slightly committed	NA	NA
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
151	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA
154	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	NA	NA
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA						

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id	B65s_SQ001	B65s_SQ002	B65s_SQ003	B65s_SQ004	B65s_SQ005	B65s_other	B69_SQ001	B69_SQ002	B69_SQ003	B69_SQ004	B69_SQ005	B69_SQ006	B69_SQ007	B69_SQ008	B69_SQ0001
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
177	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	NA
178	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	modern nutrition for plants	Very committed	Slightly committed	Moderately committed	NA	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	Slightly committed	Very committed
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA
181	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	inoculants	Very committed	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Slightly committed	Moderately committed	Not at all committed	Very committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Slightly committed	NA
193	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	NA
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	Slightly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA
216	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	Moderately committed	NA
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA
220	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA	Very committed
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	Moderately committed	NA	NA	NA
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	Moderately committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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id	B65s_SQ001	B65s_SQ002	B65s_SQ003	B65s_SQ004	B65s_SQ005	B65s_other	B69_SQ001	B69_SQ002	B69_SQ003	B69_SQ004	B69_SQ005	B69_SQ006	B69_SQ007	B69_SQ008	B69_SQ0001
235	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	during the experience framework: organisation and anticipation in order to produce its own seeds	Overwhelmingly committed	Overwhelmingly committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Slightly committed
236	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Very committed	Moderately committed	Slightly committed	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed	Very committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Very committed
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed	Moderately committed	NA	Very committed	NA	NA	NA	NA	Overwhelmingly committed

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id	C1	C2_SQ002	C2_SQ003	C2_SQ004	C4_1#0	C4_1#1	C4_2#0	C4_2#1	C4_3#0	C4_3#1	C4_4#0	C4_4#1	C4_SQ001#0	C4_SQ001#1	C4_SQ002#0
18	6	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	slightly relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
19	6	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	6	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	3	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA
26	4	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
35	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
33	4	Yes	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
36	4	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
40	8	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
42	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	5	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	5	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	8	Yes	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant
49	9	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
189	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	slightly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA
55	3	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	3	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
61	9	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA
187	7	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
65	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
66	3	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant
67	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	6	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA
76	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
77	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA
82	2	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant				
83	9	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	moderately relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
90	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
93	6	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	4	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA

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id	C1	C2_SQ002	C2_SQ003	C2_SQ004	C4_1#0	C4_1#1	C4_2#0	C4_2#1	C4_3#0	C4_3#1	C4_4#0	C4_4#1	C4_SQ001#0	C4_SQ001#1	C4_SQ002#0
96	9	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
98	9	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
99	5	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
100	9	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
103	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	slightly relevant
104	9	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
105	8	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
106	8	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
107	4	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
109	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
110	5	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
112	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant
117	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
120	4	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	moderately relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
127	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	slightly relevant
129	9	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
130	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
131	9	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
132	9	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant
134	7	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant
137	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	5	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	4	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA
142	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
143	8	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	slightly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant
145	7	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA
149	9	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
151	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
154	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
155	7	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA
156	7	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
157	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
159	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	9	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
164	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
165	4	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
166	5	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
168	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
169	3	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	4	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	6	Yes	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant

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id	C1	C2_SQ002	C2_SQ003	C2_SQ004	C4_1#0	C4_1#1	C4_2#0	C4_2#1	C4_3#0	C4_3#1	C4_4#0	C4_4#1	C4_SQ001#0	C4_SQ001#1	C4_SQ002#0
173	9	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	8	Yes	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
176	7	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
177	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
178	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA
179	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
182	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant
193	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	slightly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	4	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant
198	6	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA				
200	5	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
201	7	Yes	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA
207	3	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
211	8	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	7	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	slightly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
213	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA
215	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
216	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA
217	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
220	7	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	3	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
224	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	8	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
227	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA
228	7	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	5	Yes	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	6	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
235	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
236	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA
237	5	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA
238	6	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA

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id	C4_Sg002#1	C4_Sg003#0	C4_Sg003#1	C4_Sg004#0	C4_Sg004#1	C4_Sg005#0	C4_Sg005#1	C4_Sg006#0	C4_Sg006#1	C4_Sg01#0	C4_Sg01#1	C4_Sg02#0	C4_Sg02#1	C4_Sg03#0	C4_Sg03#1
18	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
33	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA
189	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA
61	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA
77	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA
92	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
99	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
100	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
112	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
117	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	C4_SQ002#1	C4_SQ003#0	C4_SQ003#1	C4_SQ004#0	C4_SQ004#1	C4_SQ005#0	C4_SQ005#1	C4_SQ006#0	C4_SQ006#1	C4_SQ01#0	C4_SQ01#1	C4_SQ02#0	C4_SQ02#1	C4_SQ03#0	C4_SQ03#1
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
129	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
130	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	very relevant	NA	NA
132	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
134	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
142	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant	very relevant
143	very relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant
145	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA
149	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
151	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant
154	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
157	very relevant	moderately relevant	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	NA	NA	very relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant
168	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	slightly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
177	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	very relevant	NA	very relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
193	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	C4_SQ002#1	C4_SQ003#0	C4_SQ003#1	C4_SQ004#0	C4_SQ004#1	C4_SQ005#0	C4_SQ005#1	C4_SQ006#0	C4_SQ006#1	C4_SQ01#0	C4_SQ01#1	C4_SQ02#0	C4_SQ02#1	C4_SQ03#0	C4_SQ03#1
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant
216	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	overwhelmingly relevant
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant
232	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
236	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

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id	C4_SQ04#0	C4_SQ04#1	C4_SQ05#0	C4_SQ05#1	C4_SQ06#0	C4_SQ06#1	C4_SQ0001#0	C4_SQ0001#1	C4_SQ0002#0	C4_SQ0002#1	C41_1	C41_2	C41_3	C41_4	C41_5
18	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes
32	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
40	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	very relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
189	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
60	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				
61	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
72	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
76	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
82	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
88	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
98	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
103	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
104	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
110	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
112	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes
117	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes

(continued)

id	C4_SQ04#0	C4_SQ04#1	C4_SQ05#0	C4_SQ05#1	C4_SQ06#0	C4_SQ06#1	C4_SQ0001#0	C4_SQ0001#1	C4_SQ0002#0	C4_SQ0002#1	C41_1	C41_2	C41_3	C41_4	C41_5
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
128	very relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes
129	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
132	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
134	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes
141	NA	very relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
142	slightly relevant	very relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
143	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
145	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
151	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
154	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	slightly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
164	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes
165	slightly relevant	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
171	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	very relevant	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
177	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
193	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
198	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				
202	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	C4_SQ04#0	C4_SQ04#1	C4_SQ05#0	C4_SQ05#1	C4_SQ06#0	C4_SQ06#1	C4_SQ0001#0	C4_SQ0001#1	C4_SQ0002#0	C4_SQ0002#1	C41_1	C41_2	C41_3	C41_4	C41_5
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
216	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
227	very relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
236	NA	moderately relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
238	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	overwhelmingly relevant	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected				

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id	C41_6	C41_7	C41_8	C41_9	C41_10	C41_11	C41_12	C41_other	C42_1	C42_2	C42_3	C42_4	C42_5	C42_6	C42_other
18	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA							
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
22	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA							
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
31	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
32	NA	Not selected	evacuation of digestates (see regulations)												
35	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
36	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	crops predator (Canada goose)	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
40	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yield decrease due to legume fatigue	Not selected	Demand oat decreased, market saturation					
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
44	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	costs processing							
45	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
48	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
49	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
189	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
56	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
60	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Problème de caractérisation du produit, sélection pour faire le lien	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	economic capacity of the cooperative to honour its commitments
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
187	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
65	NA	Not selected	Protein production very costly												
66	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
72	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	NA	Yes	Not selected	difficult valorisation of straw, seed is OK, but not enough to be viable											
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
78	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
85	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

(continued)

id	C41_6	C41_7	C41_8	C41_9	C41_10	C41_11	C41_12	C41_other	C42_1	C42_2	C42_3	C42_4	C42_5	C42_6	C42_other
88	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	distance between farmers, sometimes trees are a problem because their leaves are difficult to harvest vegetables.	NA						
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
92	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA											
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
95	Not selected	excess or lack of water, frost	Not selected	Cannot sell it well											
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
98	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA							
99	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
106	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
107	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA							
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
112	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
117	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
128	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
129	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
131	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA				
132	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
134	Not selected	NA	Not selected	There may be risks related to price volatility. Therefore the revenues could be very high in some years, in other years this could not happen											
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
138	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
140	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA							
142	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
143	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
145	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
149	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
154	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
164	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							

(continued)

id	C41_6	C41_7	C41_8	C41_9	C41_10	C41_11	C41_12	C41_other	C42_1	C42_2	C42_3	C42_4	C42_5	C42_6	C42_other
167	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
170	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
171	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
175	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
177	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
178	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
179	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
181	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA						
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
193	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
195	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA				
198	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA				
200	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
201	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
213	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA										
224	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
226	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA						
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
235	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	lack of recognition in the price for the effort made for a more sustainable production with less inputs						
236	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
238	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA				

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id	C43_1	C43_2	C43_3	C43_4	C43_7	C43_6	C43_other	C44_1	C44_2	C44_3	C44_4	C44_5	C44_other	C41e_1	C41e_2
18	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	regional law concerning e.g. conservation of grassland or nature protection	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected
19	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
22	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	regional regulations concerning grassland conservation or nature protection	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
32	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	storage, management, spreading of digestates // digestates considered as waste	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes
35	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
36	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected									
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
42	Not selected	Direct payments have a big impact, if there would be payments also for legumes (and not mainly ex. cereals) that would change a lot.	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
45	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes
46	Not selected	Organic farming regulation	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
51	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
189	Not selected	frequent changes in regulations regarding organic agriculture	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

(continued)

id	C43_1	C43_2	C43_3	C43_4	C43_7	C43_6	C43_other	C44_1	C44_2	C44_3	C44_4	C44_5	C44_other	C41e_1	C41e_2
60	Not selected	no premiums for hemp cultivation in Wallonia as opposed to what happens in Flanders // many controls (paranoia in relation to cannabis)	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected									
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
187	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes				
65	Not selected	Yes	Critical load of Phasin only defined in 2017	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
66	Not selected	Seed availability of yeelow and brown seeds	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
69	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
70	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes						
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes						
78	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
88	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
90	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
92	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected									
93	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
96	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
99	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected
100	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
105	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
109	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
110	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
112	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
117	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
129	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
131	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
132	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA						
134	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
140	Not selected	Conversion period ending too late for adequate seeding period	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					

(continued)

id	C43_1	C43_2	C43_3	C43_4	C43_7	C43_6	C43_other	C44_1	C44_2	C44_3	C44_4	C44_5	C44_other	C41e_1	C41e_2
141	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
142	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	these factors are characterized by a strong dualism. In fact those farmers who decided to be not involved in the diversification initiative, have taken this decision due to the increase in the labor costs required by the three-year rotation. At the same time, the farmers that voluntarily participated to the initiative, have done so for the trust established over time with Findus and the authoritative-ness of the brand. The personal relationships established over time with farmers were therefore a discriminating factor that has automatically selected the farmers	Yes	Not selected						
143	Not selected	The Environmental Legislative Decree n. 152/06, in particular for the limit values of the atmospheric emission of COT (Total Organic Carbon)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected					
145	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
154	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

(continued)

id	C43_1	C43_2	C43_3	C43_4	C43_7	C43_6	C43_other	C44_1	C44_2	C44_3	C44_4	C44_5	C44_other	C41e_1	C41e_2
156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
160	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
164	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
165	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes						
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
171	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected						
173	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
176	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
177	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
179	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
181	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
193	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected						
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
198	Not selected	-	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected					
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
202	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
213	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes						
224	Yes	Not selected	intercropping not sufficiently considered	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected				
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes						
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes						
227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
235	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Lack of direct incentive for innovation in more sustainable agriculture	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected
236	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						
237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected						

(continued)

id	C43_1	C43_2	C43_3	C43_4	C43_7	C43_6	C43_other	C44_1	C44_2	C44_3	C44_4	C44_5	C44_other	C41e_1	C41e_2
238	Not selected	artefact: aid for diversification has led to an increase of involved farms but 3 years later the aid stopped and some of them have withdrawn	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected					

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id	C41e_3	C41e_4	C41e_5	C41e_6	C41e_7	C41e_8	C41e_9	C41e_10	C41e_11	C41e_12	C41e_other	C42e_1	C42e_2	C42e_3	C42e_4
18	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
19	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes										
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
32	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
36	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected				
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
45	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
51	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
189	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes										
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
60	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected									
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
187	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected								
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
66	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected										
67	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
69	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Integrated Farming approach	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected				
70	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected							
72	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
77	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
88	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	farmers have to take attentionpoints in account for the partner they are working with	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes
90	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
92	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected									
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
95	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
96	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes										
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
99	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
100	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
105	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected					
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
107	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
109	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected				
110	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
112	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
117	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected				

(continued)

id	C41e_3	C41e_4	C41e_5	C41e_6	C41e_7	C41e_8	C41e_9	C41e_10	C41e_11	C41e_12	C41e_other	C42e_1	C42e_2	C42e_3	C42e_4
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
127	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
129	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
131	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected						
132	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
134	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
141	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
142	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes									
143	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected				
145	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
154	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
155	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
156	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected										
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
160	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Verbesserte Ausnutzung organischer Dünger. Einsparung von Miner- aldünger	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes					
164	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected										
165	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
171	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected								
173	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected										
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
176	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected										
177	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
179	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
180	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
193	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected
195	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
198	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected						
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
201	Not selected	Nitrogen fixation	NA	NA	NA	NA									
202	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
211	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
213	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
215	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
216	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
217	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
223	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

(continued)

id	C41e_3	C41e_4	C41e_5	C41e_6	C41e_7	C41e_8	C41e_9	C41e_10	C41e_11	C41e_12	C41e_other	C42e_1	C42e_2	C42e_3	C42e_4
224	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes
225	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
226	Yes	Yes	Not selected	competition with mainstream productions	NA	NA	NA	NA							
227	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes										
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA										
235	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	competitiveness facing other mainstream producers	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected
236	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes					
237	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected
238	Yes	Not selected	competition with mainstream based systems	NA	NA	NA	NA								

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id	C42e_5	C42e_6	C42e_other	C43e_SQ001	C43e_SQ002	C43e_SQ003	C43e_SQ004	C43e_SQ005	C43e_SQ006	C43e_other	C44e_1	C44e_2	C44e_3	C44e_4	C44e_5	C44e_other
18	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
19	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	regional regulations concerning nature protection or conservation of grassland	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
21	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
22	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
26	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
31	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Trust between team members and with farmers
35	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
33	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
36	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA					
40	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
42	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
43	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
44	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
45	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Biomasse 2014 - Regional project led by the Ministry of Energy	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
46	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
48	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
49	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
51	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
189	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	observation and anticipation of trends in the development of organic farming
55	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
56	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
60	Not selected	Not selected	market for the seed, well paid	Not selected	hemp has always been supported by public policies in Wallonia	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA					
61	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
187	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
65	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
66	Not selected	Not selected	Buyers willingness and interest to purchase Swiss mustard	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
67	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
69	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
70	Not selected	Yes	reducing market risk. Opening new markets	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						

(continued)

id	C42e_5	C42e_6	C42e_other	C43e_SQ001	C43e_SQ002	C43e_SQ003	C43e_SQ004	C43e_SQ005	C43e_SQ006	C43e_other	C44e_1	C44e_2	C44e_3	C44e_4	C44e_5	C44e_other
72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
76	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
77	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
78	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	regulation on farmers associations	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
82	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
83	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
85	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
88	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	need of rotation	Not selected	being open for win-win both, open minded				
90	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
92	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA					
93	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
95	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
96	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
98	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA
99	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
100	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
103	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
104	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
105	Not selected	Not selected	project funding	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
106	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
107	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
109	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
110	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
112	Not selected	Not selected	lower inputs, better resistance to pest	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
117	Not selected	Not selected	low inputs	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA						
120	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
127	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				
128	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
129	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
130	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	NA
131	Not selected	Not selected	budget available to carry on the initiative	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						
132	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
134	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
137	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
138	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
141	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
142	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
143	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
145	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
149	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
151	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	NA
154	Yes	Yes	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Udział w badaniach naukowych, wyjazdach szkoleniowych i filmach
155	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
156	Yes	Yes	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
157	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
159	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
160	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA

(continued)

id	C42e_5	C42e_6	C42e_other	C43e_SQ001	C43e_SQ002	C43e_SQ003	C43e_SQ004	C43e_SQ005	C43e_SQ006	C43e_other	C44e_1	C44e_2	C44e_3	C44e_4	C44e_5	C44e_other
164	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
165	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	NA
166	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
167	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	maintaining close relationships with consumers, mutual trust
168	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
169	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
170	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
171	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
173	Not selected	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
174	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
175	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
176	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA
177	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
178	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
179	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Regional policies	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
180	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	NA
182	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
192	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
193	Yes	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
195	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Yes	NA
198	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
200	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
201	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
202	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
207	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
211	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
212	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
213	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
215	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA
216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
217	NA	NA	NA	Not selected	Public interest in the production of food and the preservation of biodiversity	Yes	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA					
220	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	NA
224	Not selected	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Yes	Not selected	very good understanding and solidarity and conviction among partners (farmers/Agricultural chamber/Regional Nature Park of the Gâtinais)
227	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

(continued)

id	C42e_5	C42e_6	C42e_other	C43e_SQ001	C43e_SQ002	C43e_SQ003	C43e_SQ004	C43e_SQ005	C43e_SQ006	C43e_other	C44e_1	C44e_2	C44e_3	C44e_4	C44e_5	C44e_other
228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	NA
235	Yes	Not selected	NA	Not selected	areas of ecological interest (even if very moderate impact)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA					
236	Not selected	Yes	NA	Yes	Not selected	specific aid for grain legumes (pea and faba bean and lupin as protein crops)	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA				
237	Yes	Not selected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Yes	Not selected	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA